

Exploring Personality Dimensions in Workload Perception and Management: A Multifactorial Approach

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of personality traits on workload perception and management. Drawing on a sample of 109 participants, primarily from Germany, and utilizing a newly developed personality questionnaire, the research explores how Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, Openness to Experience, and Agreeableness relate to workload management. Key findings reveal that Conscientiousness and Openness to Experience are positively associated with effective workload handling, emphasizing the roles of reliability and organizational skills. Conversely, Neuroticism correlates with higher procrastination and perceived workload, highlighting emotional regulation challenges. Interestingly, while personality traits influence workload perception, environmental factors such as time pressure and comparison with colleagues play a critical role in shaping these perceptions. This research extends prior studies by integrating both personal and contextual factors, offering insights into personalized interventions for improving workload management. The findings underscore the importance of tailoring strategies to individual traits to enhance workplace performance and well-being.

Keywords: Workload Management, Personality Traits, Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, Openness to Experience, Procrastination, Emotional Regulation, Work Environment, Workload Perception, Organizational Skills

1. Introduction

Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024a) provided a comprehensive definition of workload and investigated the framework conditions, cognitive abilities, physical demands, and social competencies influencing workload management. Like in Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024a), our research aims to answer three pivotal questions but in regard to personality:

- what hinders someone from managing workload effectively?
- what helps someone to cope with the workload?
- what influences the perception of excessive workload?

Our results indicated that social competencies, including organisational skills, reliability, and situational intelligence, significantly aid in managing workload. Cognitive competencies, particularly mental flexibility and efficient

information processing were also crucial. Additionally, physical demands, such as prolonged sitting, hindered workload management. Environmental factors, such as time pressure, the pressure to perform, and overtime emerged as significant contributors to the perception of workload. Interpersonal and cognitive competencies are vital for coping with workload, and environmental stresses have a more pronounced effect on workload perception than physical demands.

Our previous research highlighted those social competencies such as organisational skills are essential for effectively structuring tasks and managing time. Reliability is crucial for maintaining consistent performance under varying workload conditions, and situational intelligence is important for adapting to changing demands and contexts in the workplace.

Cognitive competencies like mental flexibility facilitate the ability to switch between tasks and think creatively under pressure, while efficient information filing enhances the capability to organise and retrieve information, thereby reducing cognitive load. Physical demands, particularly prolonged sitting, were identified as significant hindrances to effective workload management, leading to physical discomfort and decreased productivity. Environmental factors, including time pressure, pressure to outperform, and overtime, were found to increase the perception of workload and stress, contributing to a higher sense of overload and fatigue.

Building on these findings, the present paper focuses on the evaluation of the person-related variables' influence and impact on coping with workload. We aim to elucidate how these variables help address our three core research questions. The person-related variables in our studies were primarily measured using a newly developed personality questionnaire, alongside variables addressing other strains and comparisons with colleagues. The present paper explores how specific personality traits—measured through a newly developed questionnaire—affect one's ability to manage workload. By examining the role of these person-related variables, we seek to provide a deeper understanding of how personality influences workload perception and management. This detailed analysis will help us refine our answers to the initial research questions and offer insights into effective strategies for workload management based on individual differences.

Hypothesis 1: Conscientiousness and Emotional Stability are associated with a lower perceived workload

In a study by Detrick and Chibnall (2006) about the predictive validity of NEOPI in law enforcement, significant

evidence for low Neuroticism and high Conscientiousness regarding police officers' better performance was found; however, there were more people who had a medium to high level of Agreeableness than very low to low level of Agreeableness, when it comes to the best recruited people.

Similarly, Van Aarde et al. (2017) discovered in the first meta-analysis on the validity of Big Five personality traits for job performance in South Africa, with $N= 6872$ participants from 33 studies, racially diverse samples and from various occupational fields. Evidence that Conscientiousness, Emotional Stability, and Extraversion might be used to predict technical performance and training. Also, Extraversion indicated poor academic achievement in business school. Their research discovered evidence that Conscientiousness could highly influence work performance in South Africa.

The researchers explain their findings by pointing out that participants' professions require frequent contact with clients, and collectivism is widely accepted in South African culture.

In the model of Chiorri et al. (2015) police officers' higher levels of Extraversion predicted higher levels of perceived workload - following the results of the NASA-TXL. They also found Conscientiousness and Emotional Stability to be associated with lower perception of workload.

This suggests that lower perceived workload might predict better performance, because lower Neuroticism and higher Conscientiousness could predict not only lower perceived workload but also better performance. Therefore, it validates the importance of researching the influence of personality on workload for psychological science. In their study, Chiorri et al. (2015) also found higher level of Neuroticism next to a low level of Agreeableness to be related to higher level of frustration in NASA-TLX. The researchers explain the higher perceived frustration with the fact that police officers might need more effort due to lower performance levels compared to their colleagues.

Interestingly, higher Agreeableness was related to lower perceived frustration and higher perceived temporal demands; higher Openness was related to higher effort, less perceived performance, higher perceived frustration and lower perceived mental demands. In contrast, when they scored higher on Conscientiousness, they perceived fewer temporal demands. Contrary to many other studies, in this study, it is surprising that next to Neuroticism, low Agreeableness was also related to higher perceived frustration.

Controversially, Conard and Matthews (2007) found that it is not perceived workload but lower Emotional Stability or high Neuroticism that primarily predicts stress. Participants

were only full-time undergraduates with a 94% white ethnic background recruited from psychology courses at US universities. A rather WEIRD sample appeared also in Fuenzalida & Hittner (2004) who found that changes in workload and a resulting lower performance could be explained with higher levels of Neuroticism, indicating a better coping with workload when having higher Emotional stability.

It would also mean that emotional intelligence as defined by Petrides (2009) would influence workload, including 4 dimensions among them also a social intelligence component: Self-control (stress management, low impulsiveness, emotion regulation), Well-being (trait optimism, trait happiness, self-esteem), Emotionality (trait empathy, emotion perception, emotion expression and relationships) as well as Sociability (assertiveness, social awareness, emotion management).

Like previous results, but in a cross-cultural context, Omohehin and Smith (2019) conducted a study on the influence of time pressure, nationality, and personality on students' performance with workload. They found that only nationality combined with time pressure predicted positive outcomes regarding workload management; personality factors such as Conscientiousness, Extraversion and Emotional Stability predicted better outcomes when it comes to workload management. The reason why international students performed better with time pressure might be explained by personality factors combined with a higher adaptation to requirements and motivation to stay in the country: Local students were counted as white British students and international students as ethnic minority students (Omohehin & Smith, 2019).

Following these assumptions, we assume that a higher level of Conscientiousness as well as a lower level of Neuroticism are associated with a higher perceived performance, respectively, lower workload. Because Extraversion might influence performance depending on the level of client contact, we did not investigate its impact on workload.

H2: Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, and Openness to Experience are associated with a higher relevance of perfectionism and procrastination for extra burden when having a workload.

Previously, we have seen that emotional regulation and self-control are part of emotional intelligence.

The studies of Galy, Cariou, and Mélan (2012) and Galy and Mélan (2015) (as cited in Galy et al., 2018) found that participants tend to adapt to the workload better when they experienced it as more alarming or attentive or if they felt more challenged.

In contrast, people who are not good at cognitive appraisal and emotional regulation, tend to procrastinate more often and avoid coping with workload more often, according to Pychyl and Sirois (2016).

Procrastination can be seen as negligence of self-regulation to pursue a goal (Pychyl & Sirois, 2016). According to Rice et al. (2012), it cannot be predicted by perfectionism, while showing a small association and therefore likely indicating a usually less self-critical attitude when procrastinating. The study showed that people were less stressed when procrastinating in the beginning of a university semester but more stressed towards the end of the semester, showing that time plays a crucial role regarding workload perception. However, perfectionism, which can like procrastination be seen as a personality disposition, appeared overall more impactful on feelings of psychological burden. It underlines again the significance of personality in the prediction of work-related behaviour.

More specifically, we assume that Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, and Openness to Experience are associated with higher relevance of perfectionism and procrastination for extra burden when having workload. However, some limitations are that in the study of Rice et al. (2012) more women were included in the sample and we don't know for sure whether perfectionism is seen as a burden or as a skill or technique to deal with workload, for instance when procrastinating.

H3: general workload perception influences is rated higher when compared to other employees.

Inegbedion et al. (2020) like Siswanto et al. (2019) found that a lack of competencies or respectively role alignment had a significant effect on how workload is perceived. In addition to Siswanto et al. (2019), Inegbedion et al. (2020) also found that a lack of interest as well as the comparison of workload with other employees had a significant impact on how workload is perceived and if it's evaluated as fair.

The social comparison theory states that people tend to compare themselves with others upwards or downwards (Gollwitzer & Schmitt, 2009). Like Inegbedion et al. (2020) who found a positive relation between workload balance and colleagues' workload, we assume that comparison can impact people's perception of workload. Therefore, we state that a higher evaluation of workload in general is associated with an even higher rating of one's own workload compared to that of colleagues.

H4: Extraversion, Openness to experience, and Agreeableness are associated with a higher perceived workload.

Furthermore, a study by Holman & Hughes (2021) revealed that workload increases Extraversion agency, Openness to experience, and Agreeableness ($c = .56, p.05$), which leads us to the assumption that higher Extraversion, Openness to experience and Agreeableness are associated with a higher perceived workload.

The difference from other studies mentioned above is that instead of NASA-TXL, they used the MIDUS survey, which includes five items on workload next to job discretion (Karasek &

Theorell, 1990, as cited in Holman & Hughes, 2021). Remarkably, they did not find any significant relation between workload and Neuroticism, and between workload and Conscientiousness.

2. Methods

2.1 Sample

The sample in our study, as described in Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024a), comprised 109 participants with a slight majority identifying as female (53.2%, $n=58$) and a smaller proportion identifying as male (44.0%, $n=48$). One participant identified as 'other' (0.9%), and the gender responses for two participants were missing (1.8%). This gender distribution provides a balanced perspective on workload management across different genders.

The sample's age distribution followed a normal distribution, with most participants falling within the mid-life age range of 35 to 54 years. This age demographic is critical as it often represents individuals at the peak of their professional careers, dealing with significant work responsibilities and potentially high workload demands.

Geographically, most participants (92.7%, $n=101$) resided in Germany. This concentration of participants from a single country may limit the generalisability of the study's findings to other cultural or national contexts. However, it allows for a detailed understanding of workload management within the German working environment.

In terms of employment, a significant portion of participants (33.9%, $n=37$) worked in clerical or technical occupations, which typically require specialised administrative or technical skills. Another 18.3% ($n=20$) were employed in middle management positions involving supervisory responsibilities and higher organisational

involvement. Additionally, 16.5% ($n=18$) of the participants were self-employed, reflecting a subset of the sample with entrepreneurial or freelance activities, which can entail greater autonomy but also unique workload challenges.

The participants' educational background and job roles suggest a sample that is well-versed in their respective fields, providing insights into how different occupational demands and personal competencies influence workload management. This demographic information is crucial for understanding the context in which these individuals perceive and manage their workload. Our participant recruitment strategy ensured a diverse sample in terms of professional backgrounds and workload experiences.

A detailed description about the recruitment of participants can be found in Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024a)

2.2 Instruments

The instrument's design and deployment aimed to capture a holistic view of the aspects affecting workload management, integrating personality traits with physical, cognitive, and social demands to provide a detailed understanding of how individuals cope with workload in various professional settings.

The 'comprehensive methodological approach included measures of personality, cognitive, social, physical and environmental demands as well as employee-employee comparison assessment of workload. A detailed explanation about the translation of questionnaires can be found in Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024a).

The personality instrument (Wortmann and Panahian Fard, 2024a) was designed to comprehensively assess the interplay between personality traits and workload management, inspired by the International Personality Item Pool (IPIP), focusing on key traits relevant to the work environment. Our personality questionnaire was validated by an explanatory factor analysis using promax rotation resulting in a factor structure of 4 factors, including Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, Agreeableness, and Openness to experience, each with specific statements to gauge these traits in a work context.

For Conscientiousness, items reflect dedication and thoroughness. Neuroticism items represent emotional instability and susceptibility to stress. Agreeableness items highlight cooperativeness and adaptability. Openness to experience's statements emphasise curiosity and intellectual engagement. Reliabilities were poor to acceptable (see Table 1, p.10). The factor structure and content adaptiveness from

the Big Five model (McCrae & Costa, 2008) are indicators of content and construct validity.

In addition to the personality questionnaire, the study employed a series of instruments to measure cognitive, physical, and social demands (Wortmann and Panahian Fard, 2024a). These measures were crucial for understanding how physical requirements impact workload perception and management.

Social demands were measured by assessing organisational skills, reliability, verbal reasoning skills, and situational intelligence, which are essential for effective interpersonal interactions and teamwork in the workplace. Similarly, cognitive demands measured mental flexibility or inductive and deductive thinking as well as mathematical reasoning, selective attention or imagination, speed in structuring information etc. Scales for social and cognitive demands were extracted from Fleishman's recruitment questionnaires (Fleishman, 1992, 1998) without exclusion of any item.

Adding depth to the workload assessment, we created our own adapted Workload Assessment (WLA) being inspired by NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) but added an item which measures social burden and a blank spaced method style-Likert Scale. In addition, we created another scale, which asked participants to evaluate the same WLA items with the exception that it included social comparison by asking to evaluate the intensity compared to colleagues': effort, frustration, social burden, performance, temporal, physical and cognitive demand (WLA-C). To identify other burdens that might influence workload perception, we created a scale including items on perfectionism, procrastination, and work environment stressors.

Participants rated factors such as time pressure, pressure to perform, noise, safety at work, overtime, and straining work relationships. Additional information on the creation process can also be found in Wortmann and Panahian Fard (2024a). This comprehensive approach ensured that both personal and environmental factors influencing workload were thoroughly examined.

Reliabilities of the question batteries, representing the 1-factor scales at the same time, are presented in Tab.2.

The methodological tools used to assess personality traits and workload management competencies and demands allow the following nuanced analysis of how different personality factors influence workload perception and coping strategies.

Table 2

1-Factor Scales/Question batteries	Reliability ω
Social and interpersonal competences/demands	.899
Physical demands	.916
WLA	.734
WLA-C	.769
Mental demands	.930
Other burdens	.821

3. Results

Hypothesis 1: Conscientiousness and Emotional Stability are associated with lower perceived workload.

Our results demonstrated a positive correlation between Conscientiousness and the general workload score from our newly created WLA scale ($r=.386, p<.001$), which was even higher between Conscientiousness and our second WLA-C scale ($r=.528, p<.001$).

Neuroticism didn't show any significant association with our workload scales.

H2: Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, and Openness to Experience are associated with a higher relevance of perfectionism and procrastination for extra burden when having a workload.

Conscientiousness showed a slight negative correlation with procrastination ($r = -.246, p < .01$). However, there was no significant relationship between Conscientiousness and perfectionism. Procrastination positively correlated with Neuroticism ($r = .305, p < .001$). Neuroticism also showed a positive association with perfectionism ($r = .414, p < .001$), $R^2=.138, F(1,105)=16.742, p<.001$.

In a multiple regression model, with Conscientiousness and Neuroticism as covariates, Neuroticism was the single significant predictor of procrastination, $R^2=.123, F(2,94)=6.584, p<.05$.

Openness to experience did not show any association with neither perfectionism nor procrastination.

H3: The own workload is rated higher when compared to other colleagues

There was a strong positive relationship between individuals' overall evaluated workload and their comparison of workload to colleagues ($r = .770, p < .001$), indicating that

individuals who perceived a higher workload also perceived their workload higher compared to their peers ($R^2=.593$, $F(1,98)=142.769$).

H4: Extraversion, Openness to experience, and Agreeableness are associated with a higher perceived workload.

As we didn't find a personality factor for Extraversion and Agreeableness didn't show any correlation with the general mean score of workload perception, our analysis for answering the 4th hypothesis will focus on Openness to Experience.

Our research findings showed that Openness to Experience was positively associated with workload experience (WLA: $r=.273$, $p<.05$; $R^2=.075$, $F(1,105)=8.477$, $p<.05$) and even higher when compared to colleagues (WLA-C: $r=.313$, $p<.05$; $R^2=.098$, $F(1,98)=10.624$, $p<.05$).

Finally, Openness to Experience and Conscientiousness weren't only positively associated with our Workload Assessment (WLA) as seen in Table 3 (p.10), but could also significantly predict workload experience in a multiple linear regression model, $R^2=.181$, $F(2,101)=12.241$, $p<.05$

Furthermore, to support the avatar's programmers in the development process, we extracted the 3 highest correlations between each personality dimension and items of our scales, presented in Table 4 (p.11). A moderate positive correlation between Conscientiousness and individual performance ($r = .579$, $p < .001$) was found, which persisted when individuals compared their performance to that of their colleagues ($r = .508$, $p < .001$). However, Neuroticism did not show a significant correlation with individual performance in general. There was only a small negative association between Neuroticism and comparison of one's own performance compared to colleagues ($r = -.195$, $p < .01$).

In a single linear regression model, Conscientiousness was a significant predictor of the individual's performance, $R^2=.337$, $F(1,104)=52.962$, $p<.001$.

In a multiple regression model, with Neuroticism and Conscientiousness, only Conscientiousness was a significant predictor regarding higher rating of one's performance compared to colleagues: $R^2=.248$, $F(2,100)=17.819$, $p<.001$.

Neuroticism was positively associated with longer/frequent seating (Table 4, p.11), while it could also predict it as a relevant workload contributor, $R^2=.107$, $F(1,102)=12.187$, $p<.001$.

Further relevant results of Neuroticism presented in Table 4 (p.11) were mentioned above as part of the 2nd Hypothesis' results.

The three highest association of Agreeableness with items are found in Table 4 (p.11), which are all with physical demands.

Not only was Openness to experience positively correlated with organisational skills and reliability as helpful workload management resources (see Table 4, p.11), but also found as significant predictor regarding the emphasis on organisational skills ($R^2=.323$, $F(1,105)=12.241$, $p<.001$) and reliability ($R^2=.114$, $F(1,105)=13.551$, $p<.001$) as workload management resources in single linear regression models.

4. Discussion

Our holistic approach ensured a thorough understanding of the different facets of workload. Regarding person-specific workload factors, Neuroticism, Openness to Experience and Conscientiousness were most relevantly associated with workload experiences or competencies needed for workload management.

Our first hypothesis posited that higher levels of Conscientiousness and lower levels of Neuroticism are associated with lower workload perception. Our findings didn't support this hypothesis. Contrary to Chiorri et al. (2015), we found that Conscientiousness even predicts perception of higher workload. However, there can be a bias as not only in NASA-TXL but also in our scales an item for performance evaluation and comparison was included, It indicates that while Conscientiousness increased perceived workload, it may not decrease performance. This aligns with Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024a), who also found that pressure to (out)perform was among the most relevant workload contributors.

Hypothesis 2 proposed that Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, and Openness to Experience are associated with higher relevance of perfectionism and procrastination as extra burdens when managing workload. Our results partly support this hypothesis. While for Conscientiousness higher levels are associated with a slightly lower likelihood of procrastination, only Neuroticism could predict procrastination as essential confounder regarding workload management, agreeing with Pychyl and Sirois (2016), who argue that procrastination reflects a failure of self-regulation tendencies. These findings suggest that individuals with higher Neuroticism struggle more with emotional regulation, exacerbating their workload perception (cf. Pychyl and Sirois, 2016). Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024a) also identified Neuroticism as a significant factor in confounding workload perception due to its association with emotional instability and perfectionism.

What's more, like Rice et al. (2012) our study showed that perfectionism was more relevant than procrastination when it comes to emotional distress.

Hypothesis 3 suggested that a better comparison of workload with other employees would be associated with a lower perceived workload. This aligns with Inegbedion et al. (2020), indicating that those who perceive higher workloads also believe their workload is higher when compared to peers. It further emphasises the role of subjective perceptions in workload management, as noted in the earlier study.

Hypothesis 4, which examined the role of Extraversion, Openness to experience and Agreeableness in workload perception, was only partially confirmed. While we found no significant dimension for Extraversion and no direct correlation for Agreeableness, Openness to Experience was positively related to workload experience which agrees with Holman & Hughes (2021)

Our initial question regarding what hinders effective workload management can be answered through the lens of personality traits. Conscientiousness, Openness to experience and Neuroticism emerged as significant factors; while Conscientiousness and Openness to experience aid in managing workload effectively, Neuroticism confounds it.

Further analysis of effect sizes regarding items that are mostly associated with each personality factor, showed that individuals with higher Openness to experience saw significantly reliability and organisational skills as essential for the workload management of their job tasks.

Agreeableness' most significant associations were with physical demands, indicating that for instance high agreeable individuals tended not to be impacted in their workload management by precise control of movements as important demand in their job tasks.

Our study's results give more depth to those of Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024a), by highlighting how conscientious individuals are better at managing performance, open people being more effortful and organised, whereas neurotic individuals struggle and exhibit higher levels of procrastination and perfectionism. Also, agreeable and open people appeared not confounded by some physical demands in their workload management. Nonetheless, it is too early to judge which personality factors manages the best physical workload.

The findings from Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024a) align with our results, underscoring the importance of individual differences in workload perception and

management. In particular, Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024a) found that social competencies, including organisational skills, reliability, and situational intelligence, play a significant role in managing workload. Cognitive competencies, particularly mental flexibility, readiness of mind and information filing are also crucial. Physical demands, such as prolonged sitting, hinder workload management, while potentially environmental factors like time pressure, pressure to (out)perform, and overtime contribute significantly to the perception of workload.

In summary, our findings contribute to the understanding of how personality traits influence workload management, corroborating the comprehensive insights provided by Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024a). By integrating these individual factors, we can better design interventions to enhance workload management, tailored to specific personality traits and the unique challenges they present in the workplace.

To address what helps individuals manage workload effectively, both personal attributes and work environment modifications are vital. Companies should support emotional regulation through mental health initiatives and optimise task management to align with individual skills and personality traits. This dual approach is one of the aims of the SAFE-Coach project and will be explored further in subsequent studies. Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024a) also suggest interventions such as stress management programs and personalised workload adjustments to enhance employee performance and reduce perceived workload.

By incorporating insights from Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024a), this discussion underscores the multifaceted nature of workload management, integrating both personality and environmental factors to inform more effective strategies for reducing perceived workload and enhancing performance. Future research should continue exploring these dynamics, considering both personal and contextual factors to develop comprehensive workload management strategies.

5. Limitations

This study acknowledges several limitations that impact the generalisability and interpretation of the findings. Firstly, the sample size of 109 participants is relatively small, and the predominance of participants from Germany (92.7%) limits the cultural diversity of the study. This homogeneity restricts the generalisation of the results to other cultural or national contexts, as cultural factors can significantly influence workload perception and management strategies (Wortmann & Panahian Fard, 2024a).

Secondly, the study relies heavily on self-reported data, susceptible to social desirability bias. Participants might have portrayed themselves in a more favourable light, especially regarding traits like Conscientiousness and Neuroticism, potentially skewing the results. Future research should incorporate objective measures or third-party assessments to mitigate this bias.

Thirdly, language translation issues could have influenced the clarity and consistency of the questionnaire items. Although the survey was translated into multiple languages, insufficient participation in the English and French versions prevented comparative analysis across different linguistic groups. As Cegarra and Morgado (2009) have shown, linguistic nuances can affect how questions are interpreted and answered, highlighting the need for meticulous translation and validation processes.

Additionally, the study's cross-sectional design limits the ability to draw causal inferences. Longitudinal studies will provide a better understanding of how personality traits and workload management strategies evolve over a longer period. This approach will also help identify potential changes in workload perception and coping mechanisms, offering a more dynamic view of the interplay between these factors.

Environmental factors, alongside personal traits, also play a crucial role in influencing workload perception, answering our third question about what influences perceived workload. One needs to emphasise that factors that are potentially environmental- and person-dependant, such as time pressure, overtime, or pressure to (out)perform, which are crucial in shaping workload perceptions (Wortmann & Panahian Fard, 2024a). The exclusion of specific contextual factors, such as health issues and weather conditions, which have been noted as relevant in other studies (Scherer, 2009) and social comparison as extra burden (Inegbedion et al., 2020) could be beneficial in future research. Including these variables could provide a more comprehensive understanding of how external factors influence workload perception and management. Also, our findings on physical demands and personality factors weren't satisfactory and will need further research with, for instance, optimised measurements.

Moreover, the study did not differentiate between various types of job roles beyond broad categories. Detailed job-specific analyses could reveal more nuanced insights into how different professional demands interact with personality traits to influence workload management. For example, roles with high client interaction might show different patterns compared to more solitary tasks.

While comprehensive, the instrument NASA-TLX (Hart, 2006; Cegarra & Morgado, 2009; Galy et al., 2017) used for measuring workload, might benefit from being supplemented with other tools that measure specific workload dimensions separately. As suggested by Galy et al. (2017), analysing each dimension of workload separately as own scales and with more items, improving construct validity for each workload dimensions, it could yield more precise insights into how different aspects of workload impact overall stress and performance.

Lastly, the reference group effect, where individuals compare their workload and performance against their peers, may have influenced the results. This effect can vary widely based on the individual's context and prior experiences (Heine, 2015), suggesting more controlled comparisons are needed in future studies.

While the study provides valuable insights into the relationship between personality traits and workload management, future research should address these limitations by increasing sample size and diversity, incorporating longitudinal designs, including a broader range of contextual factors, and utilising a combination of subjective and objective measurement tools to enhance the robustness and generalisability of the findings.

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Table 1

Personality Subscales	Reliability ω	Nr of items
Conscientiousness	.624	4
Neuroticism	.709	4
Agreeableness	.600	4
Openness to Experience	.758	4

Table 3

Variable		WLA	WLA-C	Neuroticism	Agreeableness	Openness to Experience	Conscientiousness	Other Strains	Mental/Cognitive demands
1. WLA	Pearson's r	—							
	p-value	—							
2. WLA-C	Pearson's r	0.770	—						
	p-value	< .001	—						
3. Neuroticism	Pearson's r	0.053	0.040	—					
	p-value	0.589	0.695	—					
4. Agreeableness	Pearson's r	0.102	0.123	-0.116	—				
	p-value	0.296	0.224	0.235	—				
5. Openness to Experience	Pearson's r	0.273	0.313	-0.044	0.197	—			
	p-value	0.004	0.002	0.656	0.042	—			
6. Conscientiousness	Pearson's r	0.386	0.528	-0.178	0.102	0.132	—		
	p-value	< .001	< .001	0.069	0.300	0.178	—		
7. Other Strains	Pearson's r	0.393	0.187	0.293	-0.122	0.003	-0.061	—	
	p-value	< .001	0.077	0.004	0.241	0.979	0.564	—	
8. Mental/Cognitive demands	Pearson's r	0.198	0.192	0.155	-0.037	0.246	-0.002	0.113	—
	p-value	0.047	0.062	0.121	0.713	0.013	0.987	0.282	—
9. Interpersonal/Social demands	Pearson's r	0.546	0.486	0.126	0.094	0.369	0.255	0.135	0.581
	p-value	< .001	< .001	0.230	0.372	< .001	0.014	0.219	< .001
10. Physical demands	Pearson's r	0.107	0.043	0.137	-0.197	-0.352	-0.073	0.396	-0.075

p-value 0.320 0.700 0.200 0.064 < .001 0.492 < .001 0.489

Table 4
The 3 major correlations within personality factors – used resources for the avatar’s programmers (ranked by effect size strength)

WL-characteristics = DV		BIG 4 (without Extraversion) = IV		
WLA	Own job performance	.579** (1)		
WLA-C	Own effort compared to others	.463** (3)		
	Own job performance compared to others	.508** (2)		
Evaluation of the physical demands	Frequent/longer seating	.320** (3)		
	Scotopic vision		-.214* (2)	-.379** (2)
	Precise control of movements		-.307** (1)	
	Coordination of movements		-.199* (3)	
Evaluation of the interpersonal/social demands	Organisational skills			.378** (3)
	Reliability			.389** (1)

Other strains evaluated as potential WL contributors	Perfectionism	.414** (1)
	Pressure to (out)perform	.357** (2)

Note.

** $p < .01$. * $p < .05$